

FoRBT - Using Mobile Augmented Reality for Making Gameplay Immersive and Engaging

Vinaya Tawde
Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic
554262@mail.muni.cz

Benjamín Kojda
Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic
550286@mail.muni.cz

Simone Kriglstein
Masaryk University
Brno, Czech Republic
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
Vienna, Austria
kriglstein@mail.muni.cz

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a work-in-progress project detailing a Mobile Augmented Reality (MAR) game that blends the digital and physical worlds, making gameplay immersive and engaging. Navigating real-world spaces requires players to make quick decisions based on their environment, fostering quick thinking and adaptability. This heightened realism can make the gameplay more thrilling and impactful. With the rise of video games as a popular form of entertainment and the unique learning opportunities presented by augmented reality, this convergence warrants thorough investigation. We present *Fury of the Red Black Tree* (FoRBT), a custom-designed mobile augmented reality game that enhances engagement and immersion by integrating real-world interaction. FoRBT focuses on two aspects of gameplay: 1) using the immediate environment for contextual integration, enhancing situational awareness and adaptability, and 2) continuous movement, enhancing hand-eye coordination and reflexes, and preventing the monotony that can occur in passive games. Future work will focus on refining the software, enhancing the game's spatial user experience, and conducting user testing.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Mixed / augmented reality**.

KEYWORDS

augmented reality games, mobile devices, immersion

Reference Format:

Vinaya Tawde, Benjamín Kojda, and Simone Kriglstein. 2024. FoRBT - Using Mobile Augmented Reality for Making Gameplay Immersive and Engaging. In *Extended Abstracts of the Expanded Animation Conference on Animation and Interactive Art (Expanded '24)*, September 5-7, Linz, Austria. 3 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12686658>

1 INTRODUCTION

Mobile Augmented Reality (MAR) games offer a unique blend of virtual and real-world experiences, captivating users with immersive gameplay and interactive storytelling. As the popularity of mobile gaming continues to surge, driven by the widespread use of smartphones and the accessibility of Augmented Reality (AR) technology, researchers and developers are increasingly exploring the potential of MAR games to redefine the gaming landscape [5]. MAR games have revolutionised how players perceive and engage with their physical surroundings, creating more interactive and enjoyable learning experiences [11]. By facilitating pairwise interactions in an AR space via smartphones, these games showcase the evolution of AR technology towards more engaging and interactive

gameplay scenarios [11]. The educational potential of MAR games is particularly noteworthy. They offer methodological guidelines for developing serious games to enhance students' Quality of Experience (QoE) [13]. Educators can create meaningful and engaging learning processes that transform traditional education methods by incorporating mobile AR-based systems. Ghazwani et al. [6] highlighted the significance of different interaction interfaces in mobile AR systems, categorising users as passive or active based on their level of interaction with virtual content. They explored opportunities and solutions for enhancing User Experience (UX) through various interaction methods, emphasising the importance of natural interaction and multiple input methods to improve AR system interactions. Overall, MAR games offer diverse interaction types that shape user experience and gameplay dynamics in an engaging, immersive environment.

The increasing sophistication of AR technology has facilitated its integration into mobile gaming, offering unique opportunities for enhancing user experience, promoting physical activity, and providing educational benefits. As MAR games evolve, they hold substantial potential for research and development in various fields, including education, health, and social interaction. This paper presents a work-in-progress MAR game that seamlessly blends the digital and physical worlds, resulting in an immersive and engaging gameplay. FoRBT allows users to interact with their environment by leveraging advanced AR capabilities, fostering a deeper connection between the virtual and real worlds. The game offers a unique, immersive experience representing the intersection of art and technology, aligning perfectly with the conference's focus on experimental and interactive visual mediums.

2 RELATED WORK

We utilised the insights presented by Tan et al. [12], where the author focused on analysing various advancements made in the current state of AR games, both in entertainment and serious gaming. Metrics like the chronology of the evolution of games, the use of technology and its advancements, and different game genres were used to gather trends and insights that benefited the development of FoRBT. Immersion and engagement are the key focus of our game, and the investigation by Marto et al. [10] on exploring dimensions such as presence, immersion, engagement, embodiment, and telepresence helped to understand the impact of AR in games. In their review, Broll et al. [2] presented an overview of the challenges of developing augmented reality games. Cross-media augmentation, player tracking solutions, game equilibration, game engine development and localisation technologies are some of the key topics

discussed by the author. While many of these authors investigated the current landscape of augmented reality games and provided an overview of trends and insights, Wetzel et al. [14] stressed the need to focus on the player experience while designing mobile AR games. The authors discussed how creating high-level design guidelines can support designers and researchers to improve the player experience while designing games. Examining the impact of usability by analysing user interaction and engagement was reported by Laine et al. [9]. The analyses discussed players' motivation and learning experiences in designing mobile AR games for education. The author discussed how interface usability significantly impacts learning by allowing researchers to compare different interaction methods on mobile phones and desktop computers. Aiming to evaluate user experiences in mobile AR games, Koceski et al. [8] collected user ratings on various aspects of the AR game interface. They assessed user impressions of virtual objects in AR and preferences for AR user interfaces (UI) over traditional 2D interfaces.

3 FORBT

Fury of the Red Black Tree is an immersive MAR game that transforms the players' surroundings into a battleground. The game leverages AR technology to project a mythical red-black tree into the player's real-world surroundings (see Fig. 1), where this sinister tree hurls red and black balls towards the player's blue ball. The objective is to skillfully navigate the blue ball to avoid collisions with these perilous projectiles and score points by surviving as long as possible (see Fig. 2). Standard touchscreen controls such as tapping, swiping, and pinching are used as interactions to manipulate AR objects, navigate menus, or trigger actions. The Heads-Up Display (HUD) in AR games is typically designed to be minimalist to avoid obstructing the real-world view. HUD elements in the game adapt based on the player's context, such as showing different information when the player is stationary versus when they are moving. The environment and challenges evolve based on the player's location and progress. New balls may appear, and existing ones may become more challenging to survive as the game advances (see Fig. 3). The game provides proximity alerts through visual and audio cues when players are near a ball, increasing tension and requiring quick reactions to avoid getting hit.

3.1 Game Development

The game was developed in Unity using ARFoundation [1]. Unity's rotation tracking supported the player's movement to encourage active participation from the player. The background effects in the game are used from the camera feed, which was achieved by creating custom materials from a modified default background shader written in OpenGL Shading Language (GLSL) [4]. Using the texture coordinates of each pixel, the aspect ratio of the screen and camera rotation together with the field of view, it was possible to compute the direction in each pixel point in the real world. The ball speed and swan rate were adjusted to progressively increase the game's difficulty.

The user interface (UI) was developed using the Unity UI system. The tree model was created in Blender [3], whereas Unity's trail renderer was used to add a trail for the player. To optimise several

features that increase the gameplay experience, Unity's ARPlaneManager [7] was combined with ARAnchors [7] and position tracking from the ARFoundations [1] package.

3.2 User Experience

The virtual objects and characters were superimposed onto the player's real-world environment through the device's camera and sensors. This creates a sense of immersion that traditional games cannot match, as players interact with virtual elements within their surroundings. FoRBT utilises gesture recognition, allowing players to act by moving their devices. Visual prompts guide the player on where to go and what actions to take, enhancing the navigational experience within the AR environment. The game encourages active participation by requiring players to move and interact with their environment physically. Unlike traditional games played from a fixed location, FoRBT encourages players to explore their surroundings, search for hidden objects, and complete challenges. This promotes physical activity and enhances the sense of immersion as players become active participants in the game world. By moving around and engaging with their environment, players feel a deeper connection to the game and its challenges. Sensory engagement is another aspect that contributes to the immersive experience of mobile AR games. This game utilises audio and visual cues to provide feedback and guide the player through the game world.

4 DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The level of immersion through active participation makes players more deeply involved in the game world. In the context of FoRBT, players must physically move and react to evade danger, heightening their sense of immersion and urgency. Active participation fosters a higher level of engagement with the game. When players are actively involved in dodging balls, they are more mentally and emotionally invested in the outcome, leading to a more enjoyable and fulfilling gaming experience. Surviving balls in an AR environment mirrors the intensity and quick thinking required in real-life situations, adding excitement and realism to the gameplay. However, this result must be taken cautiously as it can lead players to engage in risky behaviours such as running or hurrying in real-world environments to avoid virtual balls. This behaviour can be dangerous, especially if players are unaware of their surroundings. In this respect, our future work involves incorporating clear safety guidelines and warnings within the game interface to remind players of the importance of being aware of their surroundings and avoiding risky behaviour while playing. These messages can appear periodically during gameplay or when players enter areas with potential hazards.

Another factor to consider is the game's complexity from the player's perspective. In FoRBT, time is not utilised as an additional challenge, as it could pose a potential usability issue for players experiencing a MAR game for the first time. The absence of time constraints allows players to engage at their own pace and offers them opportunities to manage their emotions. For instance, if a level is too easy, it might lead to boredom; if it is too difficult, it can induce anxiety. By incorporating this feature in the future, the game can acknowledge diverse user experiences and offer various avenues for player engagement.

Figure 1: The mythical red-black tree Figure 2: FoRBT gameplay mode Figure 3: Increased difficulty level

5 CONCLUSION

This paper describes a work-in-progress mobile augmented reality game: Fury of the Red Black Tree (FoRBT). The game intends to enhance engagement and immersion by integrating real-world interaction using the immediate environment for contextual integration, enhancing situational awareness and adaptability. The game uses AR technology and gameplay to create continuous movement and improve hand-eye coordination and reflexes to prevent monotony in passive games. FoRBT aims to keep players fully immersed and engaged by using various aspects of user experience and leveraging AR technology. These aspects of the game can be used for entertainment purposes and as a mechanism to be explored in multiple areas.

REFERENCES

- [1] ARCore. 2022. GETTING STARTED WITH AR FOUNDATION. <https://developers.google.com/ar/develop/unity-arf/getting-started-ar-foundation> Last accessed:2024-05-19.
- [2] Wolfgang Broll, Jan Ohlenburg, Irma Lindt, Iris Herbst, and Anne-Kathrin Braun. 2006. Meeting technology challenges of pervasive augmented reality games. In *Proceedings of 5th ACM SIGCOMM workshop on Network and system support for games - NetGames '06*. ACM Press, Singapore, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1230040.1230097>
- [3] B. O. Community. 2017. BLENDER 3D MODELLING AND RENDERING PACKAGE. <https://www.blender.org> Last accessed:2024-05-19.
- [4] MDN contributors. 2021. GLSL SHADERS. https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Games/Techniques/3D_on_the_web/GLSL_Shaders Last accessed:2024-05-19.
- [5] Marco De Sa and Elizabeth F. Churchill. 2012. Mobile augmented reality: design, prototyping and evaluation. In *Proceedings of the 14th international conference on Human-computer interaction with mobile devices and services companion*. ACM, San Francisco California USA, 225–228. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2371664.2371720>
- [6] Yahya Ghazwani and Shamus Smith. 2020. Interaction in Augmented Reality: Challenges to Enhance User Experience. In *Proceedings of the 2020 4th International Conference on Virtual and Augmented Reality Simulations*. ACM, Sydney NSW Australia, 39–44. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3385378.3385384>
- [7] Will Goldstone. 2009. UNITY GAME DEVELOPMENT ESSENTIALS. https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Games/Techniques/3D_on_the_web/GLSL_Shaders Last accessed:2024-05-19.
- [8] Saso Koceski and Natasa Koceska. 2011. Interaction between players of mobile phone game with augmented reality (AR) interface. In *2011 International Conference on User Science and Engineering (i-USER)*. IEEE, Selangor, Malaysia, 245–250. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iUSER.2011.6150574>
- [9] Teemu H. Laine and Haejung Suk. 2019. Designing Educational Mobile Augmented Reality Games Using Motivators and Disturbance Factors. In *Augmented Reality Games II*, Vladimir Geroimenko (Ed.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 33–56. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15620-6_2
- [10] Anabela Marto and Alexandrino Gonçalves. 2022. Augmented Reality Games and Presence: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Imaging* 8, 4 (March 2022), 91. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging8040091>
- [11] M. Rocchetti, G. Marfia, A. Amoroso, S. Caraceni, and Angelo Varni. 2012. Augmenting augmented reality with pairwise interactions: The case of Count Luigi Ferdinando Marsili shooting game. In *2012 IEEE Consumer Communications and Networking Conference (CCNC)*. IEEE, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 467–471. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCNC.2012.6181002>
- [12] Chek Tien Tan and Donny Soh. 2011. AUGMENTED REALITY GAMES: A REVIEW. *Medical Reference Services Quarterly* (04 2011), 212–8.
- [13] Maja Videnovik, Vladimir Trajkovik, Linda Vibeke Kionig, and Tone Vold. 2020. Increasing quality of learning experience using augmented reality educational games. *Multimedia Tools and Applications* 79, 33-34 (Sept. 2020), 23861–23885. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-09046-7>
- [14] Richard Wetzel, Rod McCall, Anne-Kathrin Braun, and Wolfgang Broll. 2008. Guidelines for designing augmented reality games. In *Proceedings of the 2008 Conference on Future Play: Research, Play, Share*. ACM, Toronto Ontario Canada, 173–180. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1496984.1497013>